

How Many (Bed)Rooms? Hard to Detect Question Order Effects in Factual Questions

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Abstract

Researchers have shown that earlier questions in a survey may affect respondents' answers to later questions, particularly in attitude and belief questions. Primarily theorized to function through the cognitive response process whereby the prior question frames or provides a context for the latter question(s), this phenomenon is known as *question order effects*. This paper proposes and explores a related phenomenon in factual or objective questions where question order impacts responses because of conceptual confusion alleviated and revised by the following question for only some interviewer-respondent dyads.

Using data from two surveys in New York City—the New York City Housing and Vacancy Survey (NYCHVS) and the New York City Housing and Neighborhood Study (NYC HANS)—we examine the impact of question order on estimates of unit size. From 1991 through 2017, the NYCHVS asked the number of rooms, followed by the number of bedrooms. In 2021, the order was reversed. Pretesting, including replicating the questions in NYC HANS, showed that respondents often gave the number of bedrooms as their answer to rooms, correcting their answer when the second question on bedroom count was asked. Reversing the order automatically clarified the intention of room count, reducing response error.

2021 NYCHVS data showed systematic reporting of higher numbers of rooms compared with 2017 and prior cycles: fewer reports of one, two, and three rooms, and more reports of four, five, and six or more rooms. Additionally, paradata on response times and instrument back-tracking from NYC HANS indicated high levels of returning to the rooms question after answering the bedrooms question.

We share reflections on the value of close collaboration between on-the-ground field staff and questionnaire designers. We also consider the complexity of cognitive testing a replicated long-standing question where the context changes, such as the shift in New York City from conceptualizing apartment size primarily in terms of rooms to bedrooms.

Key Words: questionnaire design, order effects, paradata, response latency, back-tracking

1. Introduction

Collecting consistent, accurate information from a large group of people is difficult. Researchers have identified numerous question characteristics that can ease or impede respondent understanding, from question length, complexity, and abstraction to additional introduction or instructions to

* The views expressed here are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Department of Housing Preservation and Development or the City of New York.

response format and order (Knäuper et al., 1997; Holbrook et al., 2006; Yan & Tourangeau, 2008). Survey researchers have also catalogued specific “problems” with features of survey questions encountered by respondents or interviewers (Schaeffer & Dykema, 2011). Ultimately, questionnaire designers seeking to collect factual information should ensure a consistent understanding across respondents by crafting simple, easy-to-understand questions (Fowler & Cosenza, 2009) with clear definitions or other affordances where needed to ensure standardized meaning, even for concepts that may seem straightforward (Conrad & Schober, 2000). Even when these best practices are in place, the order in which questions are presented can shift the context within which respondents understand the question and thereby affect their interpretation and ultimately the answers provided.

In this paper, we describe an unexpected question order effect in two relatively simple, factual questions about residential unit size that had been repeated unchanged across many survey cycles and multiple decades, and which are currently administered in substantially similar form in other national surveys. We discuss the changing residential context that gave rise to the issue and document its discovery, first by on-the-ground interviewers in another large survey, then corroborated by paradata from that survey, and finally demonstrated as a large effect using non-experimental comparisons of cycle-over-cycle estimates from a large, representative citywide survey in New York City stemming from a redesign that included changing the order of the questions. Situating our analysis in a sociological as well as a psychological understanding of the response process, we consider how shifting sociocultural norms as well as historical and temporal processes can impact the social and linguistic context within which an interview takes place, thus giving rise to or ameliorating issues with survey questions such as question order effects.

2. Background

2.1 Question Order Effects

For almost a century, survey researchers have recognized that the order in which questions are asked and the resulting context can affect respondents’ answers (American Marketing Association, 1937; Sayre, 1939).¹ Early investigation focused almost exclusively on what are commonly referred to as opinion questions.² These include questions about values, beliefs, attitudes, and preferences, from political issues such as support for press freedoms of Communist reporters in the United States (Hyman & Sheatsley, 1950; Schuman & Presser, 1981; Schuman et al., 1983) party and candidate preferences (Willick & Ashley, 1971; Sigelman, 1981; Crespi & Morris, 1984) and support for legality of abortion (Schuman et al., 1981) to attitudes toward working conditions (Metzner & Mann, 1953), life satisfaction (Bradburn & Mason, 1964), and “energy, the economy, politics, and religion” (McFarland, 1981), and many other topics in between.

Kalton and Schuman (1982) pointed out that while the focus had primarily been on opinion questions, these effects may also occur with factual questions, but that the underlying mechanisms were likely different. Gibson et al. (1978) showed that including a supplement eliciting attitudes toward neighborhood safety, crime, and related topics earlier in the interview increased reports of victimization in the National Crime Survey (NCS) City Sample. Using the same data, Cowan, Murphy, and Wiener (1978) demonstrated that increased reports were of more common, less serious crimes among members of groups that generally had higher victimization rates and concluded that this was likely better, more accurate reporting possibly because the supplement better stimulated the memories of respondents with more events to draw from.

¹ Response order effects—the phenomenon whereby the order in which *answers* are presented to respondents impacts responses—have also been documented and studied extensively. This manuscript focuses exclusively on question order effects.

² Though later attention has been paid to question order effects in factual or knowledge questions, work up to the present has mainly focused on opinion questions.

2.1.1 Cognitive Response Process

Jonsdottir (2004) describes the shift starting in the mid-1980s from attempts to identify and avoid context effects toward a theoretical understanding built on collaboration with cognitive psychologists. Building on Tourangeau's (1984) seminal four-step cognitive model of the survey response process, Tourangeau and Rasinski (1988) theorized how context effects can map onto each of the four steps of the framework.

The first step is respondent comprehension and understanding of the question. Here, prior items not only make up an interpretive framework within which the respondent makes sense of the question but can also inform the respondent's understanding of the scope of the question by suggesting what information would be newly relevant rather than redundant with previous questions. In the second step, retrieval of relevant information from memory, earlier questions can have a priming effect, activating certain memories or beliefs and making them more accessible to respondents considering a survey question.³ In the third step, forming judgments based on the understanding achieved in step 1 and retrieval of information in step 2, the context of prior items can set a norm or standard of comparison. In the final step, a respondent selects an answer from among the choices provided. Earlier questions can exert pressure on respondents to edit their responses to appear consistent. The effects at each of these four stages can take the form of either carryover effects, where the reaction is consistent with previous questions, or backfire effects, where the reaction contrasts with previous questions, depending on a variety of factors.

Schuman, Presser, and Ludwig (1981) found that the level of support for abortion in general decreases when preceded by a specific question about an unborn child with a defect compared to when the general question is asked first (or alone). But the level of support in the specific case of the defect did not change. They termed this phenomenon a "part-whole" or "subtraction" effect because when the specific question is asked first, the respondent is likely to remove ("subtract") the specific case ("part") when later answering the general question ("whole"). Their findings accord with Smith's (1979) ordering of general and marriage-specific happiness questions and Kalton, Collins, and Brook's (1978) manipulation of the order of questions about standards for all drivers and younger drivers specifically.

Smith (1992) endeavours to harmonize the standard/traditional classification of context effects with Tourangeau and Rasinski's (1988) categories nested within steps in the response process. From a cognitive response process perspective, the part-whole effect occurs during the first step, comprehension/interpretation. Smith posits that the part-whole effect may function by essentially redefining the latter question—a redefinition or clarification effect. In attempting to make sense of the general question, the respondent might now discount the content covered by the earlier specific question. Though Smith's focus in the chapter is opinion questions, his example of the redefinition is a factual question relating to brand ownership. In fact, the redefinition/clarification effect could apply to any question—opinion or factual—where placing another question before it would lead some respondents to interpret the question differently.

2.1.2 Socio-cultural Interview Context

Miller (2004) contends that beyond the cognitive and psychological models discussed above, social and cultural factors can also affect the survey response process. Sociocultural differences in beliefs and attitudes are generally accepted, but such differences can also impact the response process for factual questions. In one example, traditional Mexican meal patterns vary substantially from typical patterns of Anglo-Americans, with no clear, direct analogues for breakfast, lunch, or dinner. As a result, food and diet questions structured within an Anglo-American sociocultural framework proved difficult for first generation immigrants from Mexico participating in the survey to answer. At a most basic level, a respondent must be familiar with the existence of a concept as well as the

³ See especially Tourangeau et al. (1989), showing that attitudes in surveys depend on belief accessibility, which can depend on prior related questions, especially when context questions immediately precede the affected attitude questions and are closely related topically.

language or terminology to answer a question about it. If either of these is lacking, a respondent will simply be unable to answer or will substitute an unintended concept in their interpretation of the question.

In addition to their sociocultural setting, interviews are also situated geographically as well as historically in time. Housing patterns and usage can differ dramatically by country and region as well as by urbanicity. For example, air conditioning prevalence varies in certain regions and countries, both by temperature and means. A person who grew up in the southern United States might interpret a question about air conditioning to refer only to central air. They would not necessarily consider a through-window room air conditioning unit. This may not pose an issue if the survey is regionally specific; however, if the same question were fielded in multiple locations, the pooled estimates may be invalid in either direction, depending on the definition of the survey sponsors (and their geographically specific understanding of what they hope to measure).

Consider two identical buildings, standing side-by-side in a city in the United States. Each building has two apartments, one on the first and one on the second floor. After entering through the main door of the building, each apartment in each building has a front door with a lock and a deadbolt. In the apartment on the second floor of each building live a married couple with two children each. In the apartment on the first floor of each building live the parents of one of the spouses who live on the second floor. In the eyes of the municipality charged with regulating the local buildings, each building contains two apartment units. And indeed, if you asked the residents of the first building, who were all born and raised in the local municipality, they would report that their building contained two units, occupied by two households. But the residents of the second building immigrated to the municipality ten years ago. In their country of origin, not only did they live together in one building/housing unit, almost everyone they knew lived together with their extended families in such an arrangement.⁴ Since moving to the United States, they have not locked the doors to the individual apartments a single time. In fact, the couple with the children don't even know where they would find a copy of the key to their apartment. The entire extended family living in the building spends time in both units on a regular basis and come and go as they please. If you asked them, they would report that the building contained one unit and that the extended family was a single household. In fact, they might not even understand the question when you asked how many units were in the building. And, in answering questions about the number of rooms or bedrooms, they would report all of the rooms in both apartments.

By way of a third example, someone who had only lived in a suburban area, where bedrooms are often defined by the presence of a closet, may interpret a question about bedrooms in a specific way, even if the bedroom construct intended by the survey author was not concerned with closets.⁵ The time spent by this person in suburban living and the generalization to city living is the result of structural features of demographic composition and typical housing of each of those areas as well as including an effect of the time of purchase of the house they lived in and how it was marketed.

Housing use patterns evolve and change over time, even over short spans of a few decades—and sociocultural, geographical, and temporal differences intersect. Even assuming that a questionnaire was perfectly constructed in all ways for the moment a survey was first administered, as contexts shift, new understanding and effects may emerge in later cycles or other surveys administering the same items, even among the population primarily targeted by the survey.

2.2 Residential Unit Size

The size of residential dwelling units is an important measure in the housing research world. The measure serves as the basis for defining crowding, a crucial social determinant of physical and mental health (World Health Organization, 2018). Unit size is also used to understand market

⁴ For this family, there may not even be a distinction between a building and a housing unit in a living situation like this.

⁵ See Eggers and Moumen (2013) for further discussion of the difficulties in identifying bedrooms.

conditions as well as for local, regional, and international comparisons of patterns of housing consumption.

There are various ways to measure residential unit size, some more practical in a survey setting than others. Our measures of the construct are (1) Number of Rooms and (2) Number of Bedrooms.⁶ In (1), rooms are defined as an enclosed area bounded by ceiling-to-floor walls, one or more of which may contain a door or open archway. The measure includes full separate rooms, for example living rooms, kitchens, bedrooms, and dining rooms, and excludes bathrooms, porches, balconies, halls, foyers, walk-in closets, and half-rooms. In (2), a bedroom is a room used mainly for sleeping, even if it's also used for other purposes. For example, if someone sleeps in the living room, that does not make the living room a bedroom. If a bedroom is used for other purposes as well as sleeping, for example, as an office or study, it is still counted as a bedroom. Studio apartments are recorded as having 0 bedrooms.

By these measures, the apartment in Figure 1 below has six total rooms and three bedrooms. The six total rooms include the three bedrooms, the living room, the dining room, and the kitchen. The foyer, the various walk-in closets, and the four bathrooms are excluded from the count of rooms.

Figure 1: A diagram of a three-bedroom/four-bathroom apartment with 6 total rooms.

Going back to the 19th century, as living space was sparser and rooms were more multifunctional than in the latter part of the 20th century, unit size was originally conceived of only in terms of number of rooms. Bedrooms, and counting their number, was a construct that developed later with increased broad-based prosperity and changing health and sanitation norms. As an illustrative example, in response to widespread marketing abuses in the real estate market, in late 1963 the Better Business Bureau of Metro New York and Real Estate Board of New York (REBNY) each published their own official guidance for measuring apartment size in advertisements (Ennis, 1963a, 1963b). Despite slight differences over when kitchens were a half or a full room, both organizations issued their guidelines by count of total rooms (“Standard is set for room count,” 1963). By the 1960s, bedrooms were already recognized and counted as a measure of unit size, but they were secondary to total number of rooms. The general conception of unit size changed and evolved over time, including square footage.⁷ Though the old room count system continued, counts of bedrooms and bathrooms became more common to describe apartment size, especially among younger New Yorkers and those who had grown up elsewhere.

⁶ Prior research has shown variability in room count (Kalton & Schuman, 1982) as well as bedroom count (Eggers & Moumen, 2013).

⁷ Responding to an increase in owner-occupied apartments in both cooperatives and condominiums, in 1971 REBNY issued guidelines for measuring apartment square footage as well as for converting between the room count system and square feet (Lyons, 1987).

The decennial census asked questions about housing as early as 1890, specifically if the home or farm was rented or owned, and if so, if there was a mortgage. In 1930, the census additionally collected information about value of the farm or home, or the rent paid, if rented, as well as whether a radio set was present in the home. In 1940, the census for the first time included a separate questionnaire on the condition of the nation's housing stock, the Housing Schedule. Among other questions, enumerators recorded the number of rooms. In the 1950 decennial, enumerators again recorded the number of rooms, this time asking for “the number of rooms in the dwelling unit, not including bathrooms.” The next decade, 1960, saw the first self-response for some questions. Enumerators again recorded the number of rooms (including kitchens but not bathrooms) by marking a number from 1 to 10+, and for the first time, respondents were asked to indicate the number of bedrooms in their house or apartment by marking No bedroom, 1 bedroom, 2 bedrooms, 3 bedrooms, or 4 bedrooms or more. In the decades following through 2000, decennial censuses asked all households for the number of rooms, but only asked various samples for the number of bedrooms on the longform survey. In the decennial census, the number of rooms and the number of bedrooms were always asked about separately.

Since the inception of the American Community Survey (ACS) in 2005, however, the Census Bureau has asked respondents to report the number of rooms in their home, followed immediately by asking for the number of bedrooms. The exact word choice, instructions, and response options have varied for these questions over the years and decades. Other surveys, such as the American Housing Survey (AHS), have opted to dedicate more instrument real estate to measuring unit size and ask respondents how many of various types of rooms other than bedrooms are in their home, such as kitchens, dining rooms, living rooms, etc. Table 1 (next page) provides an overview of unit size questions as they have been administered in various national surveys in the United States.

3. Data and Methods

In the present paper, we review non-experimental findings from a change in the ordering of the unit size questions in a representative housing survey in New York City, the New York City Housing and Vacancy Survey (NYCHVS). This was not a formal experiment; rather, we present purely observational data to show the results of this change in order. We also present paradata from a second study, the New York City Housing and Neighborhood Study (NYC HANS), that replicated the questions in their original order.

The main survey, NYCHVS, asked the two unit size questions in the same order, number of rooms then number of bedrooms, replicated in at least twelve survey cycles over more than 30 years. The research team at the New York City Department of Housing Preservation and Development, to which the present authors belong, following best practice and recommendations for maintaining comparability across surveys, replicated those items exactly, in that same order, in an independent secondary study, NYC HANS. The questions replicated not just the NYCHVS, but also the ACS, in form, substance, and to our purposes here, order.

For NYC HANS, the research team actively served as the field staff. From the experience of the present authors⁸ and that of other field interviewers administering the unit size questions, we experienced the problematic question order effect described in this paper. In sections that follow, we explain the analysis conducted using paradata from this secondary study as well as the resulting redesign that followed for the original, long-term study, and compare over time the representative estimates from before and after the change. The indications of this question order effect were so strong in the secondary study that we did not think the benefits of a randomized, split-ballot experiment to test the effect was worth the cost of diminished data quality in the group with the original question order.

⁸ The authors of this paper functioned as Project Coordinator and Principal Investigator of NYC HANS, respectively.

Table 1: Overview of Unit Size Questions Administered in the U.S. Decennial Census and the American Community Survey (ACS)

Survey	Rooms	Bedrooms
1940 Decennial	Q13. Number of rooms	N/A
1950 Decennial	Q9. How many rooms are in this dwelling unit, not including bathrooms?	N/A
1960 Decennial	Q8. How many rooms are in this unit? Include kitchens but not bathrooms.	Q19. How many bedrooms are in the house or apartment? <i>Count rooms whose main use is as bedrooms even if they are occasionally used for other purposes. If you live in a one-room apartment without a separate bedroom, check "No bedroom."</i>
1970 Decennial	Q4. How many rooms do you have in your living quarters, not counting bathrooms? <i>Do not count bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or half-rooms.</i>	Q26. How many bedrooms do you have? <i>Count rooms used mainly for sleeping even if used also for other purposes.</i>
1980 Decennial	Q7. How many rooms do you have in your living quarters? <i>Do <u>not</u> count bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or half-rooms.</i>	Q24. How many bedrooms do you have? <i>Count rooms used mainly for sleeping even if used also for other purposes.</i>
1990 Decennial	Q3. How many rooms do you have in this house or apartment? <i>Do NOT count bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or half-rooms. Count only whole rooms in your house, apartment, or mobile home used for living purposes, such as living rooms, dining rooms, kitchens, bedrooms, finished recreation rooms, family rooms, etc. Do not count bathrooms, kitchenettes, strip or pullman kitchens, utility rooms, foyers, halls, half-rooms, porches, balconies, unfinished attics, unfinished basements, or other unfinished space used for storage.</i>	Q9. How many bedrooms do you have; that is, how many bedrooms would you list if this house or apartment were on the market for sale or rent? <i>Include all rooms intended to be used as bedrooms in this house, apartment, or mobile home, even if they are currently being used for other purposes.</i>

2000 Decennial

Q37. How many rooms do you have in this house, apartment, or mobile home? *Do NOT count bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or half-rooms.*

Q38. How many bedrooms do you have; that is, how many bedrooms would you list if this house, apartment, or mobile home were on the market for sale or rent?

American Community Survey, 2005-2007

Q7. How many rooms are in this house, apartment, or mobile home? *Do NOT count bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or half-rooms.*

Q8. How many bedrooms are in this house, apartment, or mobile home; that is, how many bedrooms would you list if this house, apartment, or mobile home were on the market for sale or rent?

American Community Survey, 2008-2019

Q7a. How many separate rooms are in this house, apartment, or mobile home?
Rooms must be separated by built-in archways or walls that extend out at least 6 inches and go from floor to ceiling.
• *INCLUDE bedrooms, kitchens, etc*
• *EXCLUDE bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or unfinished basements.*

Q7b. How many of these rooms are bedrooms?
Count as bedrooms those rooms you would list if this house, apartment, or mobile home were for sale or rent. If this is an efficiency/studio apartment, print "0".

American Community Survey, 2020-2023

Q6a. How many separate rooms are in this house, apartment, or mobile home?
Rooms must be separated by built-in archways or walls that extend out at least 6 inches and go from floor to ceiling.
• *INCLUDE bedrooms, kitchens, etc*
• *EXCLUDE bathrooms, porches, balconies, foyers, halls, or unfinished basements.*

Q6b. How many of these rooms are bedrooms?
Count as bedrooms those rooms you would list if this house, apartment, or mobile home were for sale or rent. If this is an efficiency/studio apartment, print "0".

3.1 NYC HANS

NYC HANS is an experimental study (Goldstein & Gaumer, 2022) that evaluates the impact of affordable housing on the well-being of low-income New Yorkers. The present analysis examines 1,654 interviews with adults across two overlapping instruments, one for households without a co-resident child and one for those with one or more co-resident child. Interviews were conducted by an in-house field team in-person via Computer-Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI) from 2014 through 2018 (Waickman et al., 2019). Within these two instruments, there were 200 overlapping questions that are analyzed here, including the two unit size questions. Question types included in this analysis cover questions with Likert-type scale answer options and 1-10 scale answer options, Check-All-That-Apply questions, other multiple-choice questions, Yes/No questions, questions with open-ended numeric answers, and questions asking for a date or time.

The CAPI software produced paradata about the interview, including timestamps for the final time a question was answered. These timestamps were used to identify back-tracking. Back-tracking was defined as any timestamp for a question which is later temporally than the timestamp for a question which occurs later in the instrument. Back-tracking served as a proxy for a misunderstanding of a question (and subsequent clarification) that requires going back to change the answer, which is the exact pattern that we directly experienced in situ during interviews when we administered the unit size questions.

In the NYC HANS instrument, the Room question appeared directly before Bedrooms question, replicating the order of the NYCHVS and the ACS.

Q37/Q71. How many rooms are in your apartment? *READ IF NECESSARY: Do not count bathrooms, porches, balconies, halls, foyers, or half-rooms.*

Q38/Q72. Of these rooms, how many are bedrooms?

Interviewers could enter numerals from 0-20 for each question. A logical edit check was present in the CAPI that prevented the interviewer from proceeding if the reported number of bedrooms was greater than reported number of rooms.

3.2 NYCHVS

As described above, the NYCHVS underwent a redesign between the 17th and 18th survey cycles, 2017 and 2021 respectively. The following sections present the administration of the unit size questions before and after the redesign.

3.2.1 Pre-redesign: 2008-2017 Surveys

The sample design, weighting procedures, error estimation, and other technical details of the NYCHVS have been described extensively elsewhere.⁹ In this analysis we use data collected during the four surveys preceding the redesign—2008, 2011, 2014, 2017. In this period, the NYCHVS was administered using paper and pencil (PAPI) and therefore did not have the capacity for any built-in logical edits during the interview.

In the NYCHVS instruments prior to the 2021 redesign, the unit size questions were administered consistently across cycles, with the Room question appearing directly before Bedrooms question.

24a. How many rooms are in your apartment? *READ IF NECESSARY: Do not count bathrooms, porches, balconies, halls, foyers, or half-rooms.*

24b. Of these rooms, how many are bedrooms?

⁹ See the 2008-2017 NYCHVS Sample Design, Estimation Procedure and Accuracy Statements and other technical documentation available at <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/nychvs/technical-documentation.html>.

3.2.2 Post-redesign: 2021 Survey

The technical details of the 2021 NYCHVS have been described elsewhere.¹⁰ The survey collected data after a full redesign that included revisions to the questionnaire, expansion of available translations and language access procedures, a shift to electronic administration via Computer-Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI), a new sample design, and expansion of the use of administrative records to improve accuracy and reduce respondent burden, among others.

In the 2021 NYCHVS instrument, the unit size questions were administered in reverse order, with the Room question appearing directly *after* the Bedrooms question, rather than before, as other surveys have and continue to do.¹¹ Additionally, the word “rooms” in the latter question was capitalized to indicate that interviewers should emphasize “rooms” to help respondents recognize the difference between the two similar questions.

C1. How many bedrooms are in your [apartment/house]?

C2. How many ROOMS are in your [apartment/house]? *Count each separate room. For example, living rooms, kitchens, bedrooms, and dining rooms. (A room is an enclosed area bounded by ceiling-to-floor walls, one or more of which may contain a door or an open archway.)*

4. Results

4.1 NYC HANS

Across the 274,733 individual questions responses over the 200 questions analyzed, only a very small share, 0.57%, showed back-tracking. Five questions were identified as outliers—with back-tracking greater than 2%. These included the amount paid for summer utilities as opposed to winter (2.19%), diabetes diagnosis (3.21%), amount earned from a job as opposed to other sources (3.51%), total monthly rent paid by household as opposed to by respondent individually (4.12%), and number of rooms in unit as opposed to bedrooms (16.63%). Figure 2 shows the distribution of back-tracking by question, ordered as they appeared in the instrument.

Figure 2: Proportion of interviews where interviewer back-tracked, by question.

¹⁰ See the 2021 NYCHVS Sample Design, Estimation Procedure and Accuracy Statements and other technical documentation available at <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/nychvs/technical-documentation.html>.

¹¹ For the full instrument in all seven core languages (English, Spanish, Simplified Chinese, Traditional Chinese, Russian, Haitian Creole, and Bengali), please see <https://www.nyc.gov/assets/hpd/downloads/pdfs/about/research/corequestionnaire.pdf>.

4.2 NYCHVS

Based on our experiences in NYC HANS, we prioritized these questions for re-ordering as part of the NYCHVS redesign. We hypothesized that respondents in cycles prior to the redesign reacted similarly to respondents in NYC HANS. Asking the Rooms question first was likely to be interpreted by some respondents as asking about bedrooms, given that today it is the most common way that people describe the size of their unit. Only after being asked the Bedrooms question would this subset of respondents realize that the prior question was not asking about bedrooms, but all rooms in the unit. In the context of a PAPI instrument, the responsibility of identifying errors falls either to the respondent or the interviewer. In any interview where neither identifies the misinterpretation, the count of rooms would be systematically underreported.

For example, a person living in a 1-bedroom apartment with 3 total rooms would report living in a 1-room unit. Similarly, a person living in a 3-bedroom house with 6 total rooms would report living in a 3-room unit. In aggregate, this would lead to a substantial overcount of the number of units with fewer rooms and a substantial undercount of the number of units with more rooms. By reordering the unit size question, we would expect a decrease in the number of smaller units (three or fewer rooms) and a concomitant increase in the number of larger units (four or more rooms).

Table 2 shows the citywide count of units by number of rooms for the four survey cycles before the redesign and the 2021 survey after the redesign. Table 3 below shows the percent change for each unit size from one NYCHVS cycle to the next. Figure 3 displays this percent change graphically.

Table 2: Count of Housing Units in New York City by Number of Rooms, 2008-2021

Survey Year	Number of Rooms in Housing Unit						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6+	
2008	190,164	304,981	900,711	848,471	550,969	533,099	3,328,395
2011	202,372	297,936	920,276	864,761	555,981	510,715	3,352,041
2014	215,623	328,148	931,828	876,514	544,326	503,655	3,400,093
2017	226,725	338,369	964,797	878,995	572,307	488,047	3,469,240
2021	195,700	306,000	924,400	936,100	663,800	618,100	3,644,000

Table 3: Percent change in number of housing units by number of rooms from previous survey, 2008-2021.

Period	Net Change from Prior Survey Cycle						
	1	2	3	4	5	6+	Total
2008 to 2011	6.4%	-2.3%	2.2%	1.9%	0.9%	-4.2%	0.7%
2011 to 2014	6.5%	10.1%	1.3%	1.4%	-2.1%	-1.4%	1.4%
2014 to 2017	5.1%	3.1%	3.5%	0.3%	5.1%	-3.1%	2.0%
2017 to 2021	-13.7%	-9.6%	-4.2%	6.5%	16.0%	26.6%	5.0%

Figure 3: Percent change in number of housing units by number of rooms from previous survey, 2008-2021.

5. Discussion

In two studies, we found the existence of question order effects on unit size. This is relevant not only for the validity of collecting these specific data points for housing surveys in New York City specifically, but also for survey researchers collecting factual information. In our NYC HANS study, paradata revealed a high prevalence of back-tracking when Rooms was asked before Bedrooms. In our NYCHVS study, we saw a meaningful shift in the distribution of reported unit sizes once the order of these items was reversed.

Though we demonstrated this effect overall, there may be heterogeneity, especially as contexts take time to shift and generational cohorts have developed new understandings. For example, older adults who have lived in New York City for a longer time may continue to think about the number of rooms in their apartments before the number of bedrooms. Recent immigrants from other areas that continue to quantify unit size by room and mostly discount bedrooms may be more prone to misreport with this modified question order.

Taking both analyses together along with our direct experience of asking these questions in the field, we provide clear evidence that seemingly simple factual items are subject to question order effects. This work supports the clarification effect proposed by Smith (1992). Here, asking about the more common conception of unit size first with the bedroom questions automatically clarifies the succeeding question on rooms (a currently less common conception). This serves to improve the respondents' cognitive processing by removing an avenue for misinterpretation.

But the basis for this question order effect is broader in that it involves shifts in the underlying construct in sociocultural, temporal, and geographic terms. In the United States, and particularly in New York City, while it was common in prior decades to refer to units by room count, it has now become commonplace to describe them by the number of bedrooms. While this is currently the case, there is not guarantee that this will continue indefinitely, and care should be taken to continually reconsider what is being measured and how.

In their overview of question order effect, Rasinski, Lee, and Krishnamurty (2012) caution that “[q]uestion order effects can present serious problems when measuring change over time, whether

in longitudinal surveys or in repeated cross-sectional surveys, or even when comparing the results of different cross-sectional surveys. Unless the question order is the same for each data collection, it is difficult to know whether change (or its absence) is due to real respondent change or to question order.” Following this guidance, common practice is generally to borrow questions from other surveys, as NYC HANS did from earlier cycles of the NYCHVS. Even more common is to replicate questions survey cycle after survey cycle, as the NYCHVS did. But researchers should be aware that problems can still arise, especially in the context of shifting norms and increasingly diverse study populations. Ultimately, the best guidance is for survey designers to engage more directly with respondents, the interviewers that they rely upon, and the interview experience itself.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge the hard work and dedication of the field staff who worked tirelessly on both NYC HANS and the NYCHVS as well as the respondents who gave generously of their time and effort. Without them this work would not be possible and there would be no papers to write.

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